

Knowledge Management: The Key to Organizational Success

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Abstract

Purpose: This paper attempts to highlight the significant role of Knowledge Management (KM) in improving Organizational Success (OS). KM is widely acknowledged as a critical factor for OS at commercial banks in Egypt.

Research Design/Methodology: To assess positive KM, refer to (KM questionnaire, Jakob 2003; and Wiig, 2003) and OS (OS questionnaire Simon et al., 2011). The data of the study was collected from the employees at commercial banks in Egypt. Out of the 382 questionnaires that were distributed to employees at commercial banks in Egypt, 305 usable questionnaires were returned, a response rate of 79%. Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) was used to confirm the research hypotheses.

Findings: There is a statistically significant relationship between the dimensions of KM (creation of knowledge, knowledge acquisition, organization of knowledge, knowledge distribution, and use of knowledge) and OS at commercial banks in Egypt.

Practical implications: This research contributes to the need for organizations to practice KM in order to be able to meet contemporary intense competition, as this trend is to play an important role in enhancing OS. The study suggests that the commercial banks in Egypt can increase OS by influencing its KM. The study provided that it is necessary to pay more attention to the dimensions of KM as a key source for organizations to enhance the competitive advantage which is of prime significance for OS.

Originality/value: The study observes that there is a critical shortage in KM and that a greater understanding of the factors that influence the OS is of great importance. Therefore, this study is to examine the relationship between KM and OS. This research dealt with KM in terms of its concept and dimensions, in addition to dealing with the role of KM in promoting OS. Accordingly, the study provided a set of recommendations including the necessity to pay more attention to KM as a key source for OS at commercial banks in Egypt.

Keywords: knowledge management, organizational success

1. Introduction

Knowledge Management (KM) is a process that transforms individual knowledge into organizational knowledge (Rašul, et al., 2012).

KM is a process that helps organizations to find important information, select, organize and publish them; and it's a proficiency that will be necessary for actions like solving problems, dynamic learning, decision making (Nazari & Emami, 2012).

KM does not belong to one area; people from different disciplines are working on it. Approaches to KM are still at emerging state and the process is ongoing, till we get a complete formal approach which shall be universally accepted (Anand & Singh, 2011).

KM has emerged as one of the most important areas in management practices and established as a basic resource for firms and economies. KM is regarded as collection, distribution and efficient use of knowledge resources. It is a process of knowledge creation, validation, presentation, distribution and evaluation (Tahir, et al., 2010).

Over the past 15 years, KM has progressed from an emergent concept to an increasingly common function in business organizations. As evidence of its maturity as an area of academic study, an increasing number of journals devoted to KM and intellectual capital management have been created (Zack, et al., 2009).

KM has become such a strategic resource of organization that it is viewed as the basis of a competitive advantage in the organization (Karadsheh, et al., 2009).

There is some survey research beginning to appear in KM journals (Kalling, 2003; McCann & Buckner, 2004; Tanriverdi, 2005).

Many studies assert that adopting KM achieves a number of important benefits for the organization including improving communication and participation in decision-making (Sarrafzadeh, 2005), improving innovation performance (Gloet & Terziowski, 2004; Lurdvall & Nielsen, 2007), improving organizational performance (Darroch, 2005; Anantatmula, 2007), and improving financial performance and market value of the organization (Zack et al., 2009),

KM is a topic of increasing interest in recent times. It is a non-material resource that plays an important role in business organizations. It is also an important source essential to achieve competitive advantage for the organizations (Randeree, 2006; Kang, 2007).

The recognition that knowledge is the key resource of production (Drucker, 1994), making it the “new wealth” of organizations (Sveiby, 1997) is largely responsible for the development and implementation of KM in organizations. KM is still in its infancy and is not well understood by many organizations (Zack, 1999; Earl, 2001).

KM has become an important subject since knowledge is considered as a competitive element for individuals, firms and nations. Knowledge about competitive, customers, products, processes and past successes and failures is considered as an asset for the organization in the twenty-first century. KM evolves from a distinct responsibility to a strategic component of a business solution (Dyer & McDonough, 2001).

The objective of KM is not to manage all knowledge, but to manage the knowledge which is most essential to the development organizations. KM can help such a stage to enhance and expand the innovation process (Parikh, 2001).

2. Literature Review

2.1. Knowledge Management

KM is a set of processes designed to find and manage positive and negative critical knowledge functions in different kinds of operations, identify new products or strategies and achieve a number of other, highly targeted objectives (Wiig, 1995).

KM is knowledge creation, which is followed by knowledge interpretation, knowledge dissemination, use retention and refinement (De Jarnet, 1996).

KM is allowing organizations to explicitly enable and enhance the productivity of generation, codification, and transfer activities and to leverage their value for the group as well as for the individual (Ruggle, 1997).

KM can be defined as leveraging the intellectual assets of the company to meet defined business objectives (Sveiby, 1997).

KM is the explicit control and management of knowledge within an organization aimed at achieving the company's objectives (Spek & Spijervet, 1997).

KM is the activity which is concerned with strategy and tactics to manage human centered assets (Brooking, 1997).

KM is the systematic underpinning, observation, instrumentation, and optimization of the firm's knowledge economies (Demarest, 1997).

KM is the development of processes to link knowledge requirements to business strategies and representation of individual and organizational knowledge (Ernst & Young, 1998).

KM is the identification either in the form of explicit knowledge held in artifacts or tacit knowledge possessed by individuals or communities (Snowden, 1998).

KM is an attempt to do something useful with knowledge, to accomplish organizational objectives through the structuring of people, technology and knowledge content (Davenport & Prusak, 1998).

KM is concerned with the whole spectrum of data, information, and knowledge, whether general or specific, explicit or tacit, shared or individual, recorded or not (KPMG, 1998).

KM is identifying the collective knowledge in an organization to help the organization compete (Von Krogh, 1998).

KM is the practices which facilitate the efficient creation and exchange of knowledge on an organization-wide level in order to enhance the quality of decision making (Delphi, 1998).

KM is questions of knowledge production, reproduction, distribution, application, and logistics depending on who the specific bearer, mediator or multiplier of organizational knowledge is (Schuppel et al., 1998).

KM is the process of identifying, creating, capturing, and applying knowledge to exploit new opportunities and enhance organizational performance (Bassi, 1999; Zack, 1999).

KM is the process of systematically and actively managing and leveraging the stores of knowledge in an organization. KM is regarded as the set of various processes to manage organizational knowledge (Laudon & Laudon, 1999).

KM is an organized and systemic process for acquiring, organizing and exchanging knowledge among employees to effectively utilize knowledge (Alavi & Leidner, 1999).

KM is a formal, directed process of determining what information a company has that could benefit others in the company and then devising ways to making it easily available (Liss, 1999).

KM is the process of creating, capturing, and using knowledge to enhance organizational performance (Bassi, 1999).

KM is any process of creating, acquiring, capturing, sharing and using knowledge, to enhance learning and performance in organizations (Scarbrough & Swan, 1999).

KM is the systematic process, by which knowledge needed for an organization to succeed is created, captured, shared and leveraged (Rumizen, 2002).

KM refers to a broad collection of organizational practices and approaches related to generating, capturing, disseminating know-how and other content relevant to the organization's business (American Productivity and Quality Association, 2002).

KM is the technique to enhance and abridge the process of implementing sharing, distributing, creating and comprehending the knowledge of the organization (Gottschalk, 2002).

KM is a structure based on past experience and build new mechanisms for exchanging and generating new knowledge (Miltiadis et al., 2002).

KM looks at how an organization adapts to changing conditions in order to survive (Burn, et al., 2002).

KM is a set of procedures, infrastructures and technical and managerial tools, designed towards creating, sharing, leveraging information and knowledge within and across organizations (Bounfour, 2003).

KM is the design, review and implementation of both social and technological processes to improve the application of knowledge, in the collective interest of stake holders (Standards Australia, 2003).

KM is a process which contains creation, acquisition, incorporation, allocation, and application of knowledge to advance the operation efficiency and competitive advantage of an organization. KM presents the exact information to the exact group at the correct time (Albers & Brewer, 2003).

KM is the systematic, explicit and deliberate building, renewal and application of knowledge to maximize an enterprise's knowledge-related effectiveness and returns on its knowledge assets and to renew them constantly (Wiig, 2003).

KM is the methodical means of administrating this valuable resource, by promoting an incorporated approach to identifying, capturing, structuring, organizing, retrieving, sharing, and evaluating an enterprise's knowledge assets (Kim et al., 2004).

KM builds on earlier approaches of data management and information management and adds a higher level of complexity with the inclusion of meaning, networking, collaboration and business process improvement (AGIMO Knowledge Management, 2004).

KM promotes an integrated approach to identifying, capturing, retrieving, sharing and evaluating all enterprises information assets which include databases, documents, policies, procedures, and experience stored in individual's heads (Malhotra & Galletta, 2005).

KM is a methodical leveraging of data, information, and different structures of assets and resources to enhance organizational innovation, reaction, efficiency and capability (Goh, 2005).

KM is the knowledge-based management, connecting people to people and people to information to create competitive advantage. KM is a systematic and integrative process of coordinating organization wide activities of acquiring, creating, storing, sharing, diffusing and deploying knowledge by individuals and groups, in pursuit of organizational goals (Nonaka, 2007).

KM is based on the idea that an organization's most valuable resource is the knowledge of its people (National Electronic Library for Health, 2008).

KM is understood to be an umbrella term encompassing the many unique but related facets of knowledge-exchange, transfer and uptake among them (Dubois & Wilkerson, 2008).

KM is a procedure, process or practice to accomplish process about knowledge, process for knowledge, and process from knowledge which leads to improve the internal and external operation (Alryalat & Alhawari, 2008).

KM is a structured process with activities to capture, discover, create, filter, evaluate, store, share and apply knowledge from individuals to advance business processes and meet organization's objectives and goals (Karadsheh, et al., 2009).

KM is a human resource management exercise than a technology based discipline. It is not merely state of the art technology used to improve efficiency of the knowledge. Rather it is an exercise about how people can be motivated, best utilize their knowledge, experiences and enhance the creativity by using state of the art technology (Tahir, et al., 2010).

Researchers have identified many aspects to Knowledge Management Process (KMP): experiencing, observation, conceptualization, and experimentation (Kolb, 1984); problem solving, implementing and integrating, experimenting, and importing knowledge (Leonard-Barton, 1995).

KMP is divided into three factors. Knowledge acquisition means the development of skills, insights, and relationships. Knowledge dissemination means the dissemination of what has been learned. Utilization means the integration of learning so it is broadly available and can be generalized to new situations (Nevis, et al., 1995).

KMP is divided into five elements. Construction is the process through which new material is added or replaced within the collective stock of knowledge. Organization is the process by which bodies of knowledge are related to each other. Observation has passed the test and been socially ratified as knowledge, it concerned with storing. Distribution is a critical issue in any organization. Application is concerned with possibility of obtaining the kind of performance improvement (Pentland, 1995).

KMP is divided into creation, manifestation, use, and transfer. Creation and manifestation is related to how it is created and manifested in people's minds and in procedures, culture and even technology. Use is concerned with how it is used in making decisions and other knowledge-related work by individuals and businesses. Transfer is related to how we learn and how we otherwise can capture and exchange knowledge (Wiig, 1995).

KMP is made up of sharing tacit knowledge, creating concepts, justifying concepts, building an archetype, and cross leveling knowledge (Nonaka & Takeuchi, 1995); applying, sharing, creating, identifying, collecting, adapting, and organizing knowledge (Arthur & APQC, 1996).

KMP is divided into four factors. Construction refers to the process of discovering or structuring a kind of knowledge. Embodiment refers to the process of choosing a container for knowledge. Dissemination refers to the human processes and technical infrastructure that make embodied knowledge available to the people within firm. Use refers to the ultimate objective of any KM (Demarest, 1997).

KMP is divided into three elements. Knowledge generation includes activities which bring to light knowledge. Knowledge codification is the capture and representation of knowledge so that it can be re-used either by an individual or by an organization. Knowledge transfer involves the movement of knowledge form one location to another and its subsequent absorption (Ruggle, 1997).

KMP consists of capturing, sharing, leveraging and feeding process (Delphi, 1998); planning, acquiring, applying, and assessing (Ernst & Young, 1998); acquisition, codification, codification, retrieval, embedding, problem analysis and solving, and knowledge shaping (Jang & Lee, 1998); creation, application, exploitation, sharing and dissemination, encapsulation, sourcing, and learning (KPMG, 1998); knowledge generation, processing, storage, dissemination, and use/reuse (Pan & Scarbrough, 1998); knowledge goal, identification, acquisition, development, distribution, preservation, use, and measurement (Probst et al., 1999); use and multiplication, development and acquisition, and transfer, institutionalization (Schuppel, et al., 1998).

KMP is divided into accumulation, integration, and reconfiguration. The accumulation of knowledge can be achieved through the acquisition of knowledge from external sources and internal creation. The major management processes are integrating and reconfiguring them according to the environmental changes (Lee & Kim, 2001).

Wiig, 2003 presents a model for the processes of KM, which include five main stages, a process of knowledge creation, knowledge acquisition, knowledge organization, knowledge distribution, and use of knowledge. This can be illustrated as follows:

1. **Knowledge Creation** indicates the organization's ability to identify information needs in a scientific manner. Views and experiences are codified in order to bridge the knowledge gap between departments and divisions, in addition to providing data to solve the problems of administrative organization.
2. **Knowledge Acquisition** is the organization's ability to acquire knowledge, store and keep it in order to use it. This acquisition of knowledge occurs from different sources, such as similar organizations which operate in the same area, the scientific and academic institutes, libraries, the Intranet, and any other sources.
3. **Knowledge Organization** is the organization's ability to classify knowledge and convert it to useful written materials (knowledge base), using modern technological methods. This contributes to achieving benefits for the organization.
4. **Knowledge Distribution** is the organization's ability to disseminate knowledge to the level of administrative organization, and every individual within each level of an administrative unit, whether by e-mail, meetings, training courses or other.
5. **Use of Knowledge** is the organization's ability to benefit from knowledge, and its circulation among all employees in order to increase functional skills, and creative abilities, which lead to improved quality of service provided by the organization to its customers.

2.2. Organizational Success

"Success" in English, according to (Webster, 1974) means end your access to what is best, or access to excel.

In French, according to (Robert, 1983) "Reussite" means getting a new result, and the means to reach or attain higher. With respect to Organizational Success (OS), there is still some confusion and lack of clarity of methodological and procedural frameworks.

Growth is an indicator for measuring OS. It means efficiency or the organization's ability to achieve its objectives in the long term, through expansion, renovation and survival (Whetten, 1987).

Regarding success through financial performance, operational productivity and efficiency, profits, target return, improvement programs in total quality management framework, re-engineering of reference and comparison is a narrow view that does not define success in the long-term in light of competitive markets. Success in the long-term lies in the organization's ability to do better things than competitors do. This is through owning distinct and fundamental capabilities that can not be imitated; besides ability to get on a competitive center of excellence (Hill & Jones, 2001).

OS is the organization's ability to achieve long-term goals and balance between the goals and objectives of the organization of employees (Kenny, 2001).

OS is the organization's ability to coordinate activities in all components linking this to a common vision to achieve its strategic goals. (Dell & Kramer, 2003).

The basic elements of OS may be expressed in the form of an equation: OS = message + strategic goals + outstanding performance (Whitney, 2010).

There are two approaches for OS in all different organizations. The first approach to OS is the economic gateway. It is based on the competitive advantage stemming from the distinct market place. The first set for the performance of the organization is the external environment of the structure of the competition environment industry (Ambrosini, 2003). This includes approaches of forces of competition (Porter), innovation (Schumpeter), and scenario analysis, which is characterized by a vision of the future opportunities and environmental threats, besides forecasting analysis of the competitive advantages (Grant, 2000).

The second approach to OS is based on the relatively modern resources approach, which confirms the possibility of looking at the organization as a package of resources to enable them to get a sustainable competitive advantage (Ambrosini, 2003). This approach is mainly based on a study (Selznick, 1957) about

the distinctive competencies, and Penrose (1959) that the organization is a collection of resources and their performance depends on their ability to use these resources. This includes the approach of the value chain to analyze the strategic capabilities that can be converted into essential competencies that support competitive advantage analysis (Hitt, et al., 2001).

3.1. Methodology

3.1. Research Model

The proposed comprehensive conceptual model is presented in Figure (1). The diagram below shows that there is one independent variable of KM. There is one dependent variable of OS. It shows the rational links among the variables. The research model is as shown in the following figure.

Figure (1)

Proposed Comprehensive Conceptual Model

The research framework suggests that KM has an impact on OS. KM as measured consisted of knowledge creation, knowledge acquisition, knowledge organization, knowledge distribution, and use of knowledge (Jakob 2003; and Wiig, 2003). Organizational success is measured in terms of organizational survival and organizational growth (Simon et al., 2011).

3.2. Research Questions and Hypotheses

The researcher found the research problem through two sources. The first source is to be found in previous studies, and it turns out that there is a lack in the number of literature reviews that dealt with the analysis of the relationship between KM and OS at commercial banks in Egypt. This called for the researcher to test this relationship in the Egyptian environment. The second source is the pilot study, which was conducted in an interview with (30) employees in order to identify the relationship between KM and OS. The researcher found several indicators notably the important and vital role that could be played by KM in reinforcing OS at commercial banks in Egypt. As a result of the discussions given above, the research questions are as follows:

- Q1: What is the nature and extent of the relationship between KM (knowledge creation) and OS at commercial banks in Egypt?
- Q2: What is the nature of the relationship between KM (knowledge acquisition) and OS at commercial banks in Egypt?
- Q3: What is the extent of the relationship between KM (knowledge organization) and OS at commercial banks in Egypt?
- Q4: What is the relationship between KM (knowledge distribution) and OS at commercial banks in Egypt?.

Q5: What is the nature and extent of the relationship between KM (use of knowledge) and OS at commercial banks in Egypt?

There are studies in literature that study KM and OS factors separately and within the frame of bilateral relation but there is no study to find that examines these two factors collectively at the Egyptian environment. This study aims to contribute to the literature by examining the research variables collectively and reveal the interaction between the research variables. As a result of the discussions given above, the following hypotheses were developed to test the effect of KM on OS at commercial banks in Egypt.

The following hypotheses were developed to test if there is significant correlation between KM and OS.

H1: There is no statistically significant relationship between KM (knowledge creation) and OS at commercial banks in Egypt.

H2: KM (knowledge acquisition) of employees has no statistically significant effect on OS at commercial banks in Egypt.

H3: There is no statistically significant relationship between KM (knowledge organization) and OS at commercial banks in Egypt.

H4: KM (knowledge distribution) of employees has no statistically significant impact on OS at commercial banks in Egypt.

H5: There is no statistically significant relationship between KM (use of knowledge) and OS at commercial banks in Egypt.

3.3. Population and Sample

The population of the study included all employees at commercial banks in Egypt. The total population is 2839 employees. Determination of sample size was calculated using the formula (Daniel, 1999) as follows:

$$n = \frac{N \times (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}{d^2 (N-1) + (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}$$

The number of samples obtained by 382 employees at commercial banks in Egypt is presented in Table (1).

Table (1) Distribution of the Sample Size

Bank Type	Number of Population	Percentage	Sample Size
1. General Commercial Banks	52564	79%	382 X 79% = 302
2. Joint Commercial Banks	11977	18%	382 X 18% = 69
3. Foreign Branches of Banks	1995	3%	382 X 3% = 11
Total	66536	100%	382 X 100% = 382

Source: Egyptian Central Bank, Economic Magazine, 2015

Table (2) describes some of the features of the respondents at commercial banks in Egypt who participated in the survey.

Table (2) Demographic Variables Frequency Distributions

	Variables	Number	Percentage
1- Job Title	General Manager	20	6.6%
	Deputy General Manager	23	7.5%
	Agent General Manager	23	7.5%
	Deputy Manager	31	10.2%
	Controller	38	12.5%
	Excellent Banker	46	15.1%
	Banker A	40	13.1%
	Banker B	84	27.5%
	Total	305	100%
2- Marital Status	Married	216	70.8%
	Single	89	29.2%
	Total	305	100%
3- Age	Less than 30 years	120	39.3%
	From 30 to 45	145	47.5%
	More than 45	40	13.1%
	Total	305	100%
4- Educational Level	University Education	140	45.9%
	Post Graduate Studies	165	54.1%
	Total	305	100%
5- Period of Experience	Less than 5 years	60	19.7%
	From 5 to 10	215	70.5%
	More than 10	30	9.8%
	Total	305	100%

3.4. Procedure

The goal of this study was to identify the relationship between KM and OS at commercial banks in Egypt. A survey research method was used to collect data. The questionnaire included three questions, relating to KM, OS, and biographical information of employees at commercial banks in Egypt. Data collection took two months. Survey responses were 79%, 305 completed surveys out of the 382 distributed.

3.5. Research Variables and Methods of Measuring

3.5.1. Knowledge Management Scale

The present study has investigated KM as an independent variable. Aspects of KM include knowledge creation, acquisition, organization, distribution, and use of knowledge. The researcher has drawn on the scale of Jakob (2003) and Wiig (2003) for measuring KM.

This measure consists of 25 statements: five statements for knowledge creation, five statements for knowledge acquisition, five statements for knowledge organization, five statements for knowledge distribution, and five statements for use of knowledge. The survey form has been used as a key tool to collect data to measure KM at commercial banks in Egypt.

KM has been measured by the five- item scale of Likert of agreement or disagreement where each statement has five options. The informant should select the answer that suits his choice, where (5) indicates full agreement while (1) indicates full disagreement, with neutral degrees in- between.

3.5.2. Organizational Success Scale

The researcher will depend on the scale developed by (Simon et al., 2011), in measuring organizational success, which has been divided into two main components (organizational survival and organizational growth). The 10-item scale organizational success section is based on Simon, et al., 2011. There were five items measuring organizational survival and five items measuring organizational growth. The survey form has been used as a key tool to collect data to measure organizational success at commercial banks in Egypt.

Responses to all items scales were anchored on a five (5) point Likert scale for each statement ranging from (5) “full agreement,” (4) for “agree,” (3) for “neutral,” (2) for “disagree,” and (1) for “full disagreement.”

3.6. Data Analysis and Testing Hypotheses

The researcher has employed the following methods: (1) Cronbach's alpha or ACC, (2) (MRA), and (3) F- test and T-test. All these tests are found in SPSS.

4. Hypotheses Testing

4.1. Evaluating Reliability

Before testing the hypotheses and research questions, the reliability of KM and OS were assessed to reduce errors of measuring and maximizing constancy of these scales. To assess the reliability of the data, Cronbach's alpha test was conducted.

Table (3) shows the reliability results for KM and OS. All items had alphas above 0.70 and were, therefore, excellent, according to Langdrige's (2004) criteria.

Table (3) Reliability of KM and OS

Variables	The Dimension	Number of Statement	ACC
KM	Knowledge Creation	5	0.7454
	Knowledge Acquisition	5	0.7758
	Knowledge Organization	5	0.6732
	Knowledge Distribution	5	0.6764
	Use of Knowledge	5	0.7666
	Total Measurement	25	0.9391
OS	Organizational Survival	5	0.9306
	Organizational Growth	5	0.8734
	Total Measurement	10	0.9505

Regarding Table (3), the 25 items of KM are reliable because the ACC is 0.9391. Knowledge creation, which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.7454. Knowledge acquisition, which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.7758. Furthermore, knowledge organization, which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.6732. Knowledge distribution, which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.6764. Use of knowledge, which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.7666. Thus, the internal consistency of KM can be acceptable.

According to Table (3), the 10 items of OS are reliable because the ACC is 0.9505. The organizational survival, which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.9306. The 5 items related to organizational growth are reliable because ACC is 0.8734. Thus, the reliability of OS can be acceptable.

Accordingly, two scales were defined, KM (25 variables), where ACC represented about 0.9391, and OS (10 variables), where ACC represented 0.9505.

4.2. Correlation Analysis

The researcher calculated means and standard deviations for each variable and created a correlation matrix of all variables used in hypothesis testing. Arithmetic mean and standard deviation values related to dependent and independent variables of this study and correlation coefficients between these variables are given in Table (4).

Table (4) Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Matrix of Constructs

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Knowledge Creation	3.82	0.729	1					
2. Knowledge Acquisition	3.78	0.741	0.981**	1				
3. Knowledge Organization	3.59	0.746	0.703**	0.695**	1			
4. Knowledge Distribution	3.60	0.755	0.698**	0.689**	0.996**	1		
5. Use of Knowledge	3.77	0.748	0.983**	0.998**	0.694**	0.687**	1	
6. Organizational Success	3.67	0.890	0.525**	0.496**	0.420**	0.431**	0.490**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level.

According to Table (4), the first issue examined was the different facets of KM. Among the various facets of KM, those who responded identified the presence of a knowledge creation (M=3.82, SD=0.729). This was followed by knowledge acquisition (M=3.78, SD=0.741), knowledge organization (M=3.59, SD=0.746), knowledge distribution (M=3.60, SD=0.755), and use of knowledge (M=3.77, SD=0.748).

The second issue examined was the different facets of OS (organizational survival, and organizational growth). Most of the respondents identified the overall OS (M=3.67, SD=0.890).

According to Table (4), KM dimensions have positive and significant relation with OS dimensions. The correlation between KM (knowledge creation) and OS is 0.525. For KM (knowledge acquisition) and OS, the value is 0.496 whereas KM (knowledge organization) and OS show correlation value of 0.420. For KM (knowledge distribution) and OS, the value is 0.431 whereas KM (use of knowledge) and OS show correlation value of 0.490.

Finally, Table (4) proves that there is a significant and positive correlation between KM and OS. So our hypothesis is supported and it can be said that there is a significant and positive correlation between KM and OS.

4.3. The Relationship between KM (Knowledge Creation) and OS

The relationship between KM (Knowledge Creation) at commercial banks in Egypt is determined. The first hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between KM (Knowledge Creation) and OS at commercial banks in Egypt.

Table (5) MRA Results for KM (Knowledge Creation) and OS

The Variables of KM (Knowledge Creation)	Beta	R	R ²
1. The bank identifies information needs to be able to provide them.	0.277**	0.322	0.103
2. The bank employs scientific research in the provision of knowledge related to its objectives.	0.006	0.369	0.136
3. Views and experiences are recorded and saved in the database.	0.223**	0.363	0.131
4. The bank's seeking to provide data to fill the knowledge gap.	0.411**	0.519	0.269
5. The availability of bank data helps employees to solve problems that face them.	0.040	0.296	0.072
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients ▪ Coefficient of Determination ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.594	
		0.353	
		32.643	
		5, 299	
		3.57	
		0.05	

** P < 0.01

Table (5) proves that there is a relationship between KM (Knowledge Creation) and OS at significance level of 0,000. As a result of the value of R², the 5 independent variables of knowledge creation can explain 35.3% of the total differentiation in OS level.

For the results of a structural analysis of the MRA, the direct effect of KM (Knowledge Organization) and OS is obtained. Because MCC is 0.521, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

4.6. The Relationship between KM (Knowledge Distribution) and OS

The relationship between KM (Knowledge Distribution) and OS at commercial banks in Egypt is determined. The fourth hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between KM (Knowledge Distribution) and OS at commercial banks in Egypt.

Table (8) proves that there is a relationship between KM (Knowledge Distribution) and OS at significance level of 0,000. As a result of the value of R², the 5 independent variables of knowledge distribution can explain 27.4% of the total differentiation in OS level.

For the results of a structural analysis of the MRA, the direct effect of KM (Knowledge Distribution) and OS is obtained. Because MCC is 0.524, it is concluded that there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table (8) The Relationship between KM (Knowledge Distribution) and OS

The Variables of KM (Knowledge Distribution)	Beta	R	R ²
1. The bank distributes knowledge through e-mail.	0.130*	0.266	0.070
2. The bank wishes issue bulletins for the knowledge distribution.	0.263**	0.257	0.066
3. The bank provides time and the right atmosphere for the exchange of knowledge.	0.090	0.215	0.046
4. There is a bank system that contributes to the distribution of knowledge.	0.024	0.260	0.067
5. The bank uses the meetings as a means to distribute knowledge.	0.433**	0.428	0.183
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients ▪ Coefficient of Determination ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.524 0.274 22.618 5, 299 3.57 0.05	
** P < 0.01 * P < 0.05			

4.7. The Relationship between KM (Use of Knowledge) and OS

The relationship between KM (Use of Knowledge) and OS at commercial banks in Egypt is determined. The fifth hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between KM (Use of Knowledge) and OS at commercial banks in Egypt.

Table (9) The Relationship between KM (the Use of Knowledge) and OS

The Variables of KM (Use of Knowledge)	Beta	R	R ²
1. Uses the knowledge among employees in the same administrative level of the bank.	0.399**	0.506	0.256
2. Knowledge is traded among workers in the different administrative levels within the bank	0.127	0.331	0.109
3. The use of knowledge increases the functional skill of employees	0.043	0.362	0.131
4. The use of knowledge helps employees to raise the level of service provided to the customers	0.047	0.263	0.069
5. The use of knowledge helps staff creativity and development	0.235**	0.322	0.103
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients ▪ Coefficient of Determination ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.568 0.323 28.509 5, 299 3.57 0.05	
** P < 0.01			

As Table (9) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.568. This means that OS has been significantly explained by the 5 independent variables of use of knowledge.

Furthermore, the R^2 of 0.323 indicates that the percentage of the variable interprets the whole model, that is, 32.3%. It is evident that the five independent variables of use of knowledge justified 32.3% of the total factors of OS. Hence, 67.7% are explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

5. Research Findings

The present study on analyzing the role of KM to improve the OS at commercial banks in Egypt reveals a set of results that deserve study and attention. The most important of these results are summarized as follows:

1. There is a significant relationship between KM and OS at commercial banks in Egypt. KM plays an important role in influencing OS. Also, KM contributes significantly to reinforcing OS.
2. KM was positively related with OS at commercial banks in Egypt. Overall findings from this study suggested that KM does affect OS.
3. There is a significant relationship between KM and OS at commercial banks in Egypt. In other words, knowledge creation, which is an integral part of KM, significantly and positively influences OS.
4. KM was positively related with OS at commercial banks in Egypt. In other words, KM (knowledge acquisition) was positively related with OS.
5. There is a positive relationship between the types of KM and OS of employees at commercial banks in Egypt. In other words, knowledge organization, which is an integral part of KM, positively correlated with OS.
6. There is a significant relationship between KM and OS at commercial banks in Egypt. In other words, knowledge distribution, which is an integral part of KM, significantly and positively influences OS.
7. This study concluded that the KM was positively related with OS at commercial banks in Egypt. In other words, KM (use of knowledge) was positively related with OS.
8. There is a positive relationship between the types of KM (knowledge creation, knowledge acquisition, knowledge organization, knowledge distribution, and use of knowledge) and OS at commercial banks in Egypt. In other words, KM affects OS.

6. Research Recommendations

In the light of previous results, the researcher completed a set of recommendations, the most important of which are as follows:

1. Officials at commercial banks in Egypt should deepen the concept of KM and its importance to all employees, as well as access to best practices in KM and application through specialized training programs that aim to develop the capacity of workers and develop their skills and knowledge.
2. Knowledge will lead to higher levels of customer satisfaction through the establishment of commercial banks in Egypt to provide services of better quality. This leads to increased revenues.
3. Designing and implementing a range of training programs for all officials at commercial banks in Egypt for the development and improvement of KM in terms of knowledge creation, acquisition, organization, distribution and use. This can be done through the development of awareness among officials at commercial banks in Egypt. That means that KM plays an important role in improving the OS to achieve customer satisfaction with the service provided by commercial banks in Egypt.
4. Allocation of a separate unit dedicated to developing KM activities and working on the follow-up and development of KM at commercial banks in Egypt.
5. The commitment of all the different categories of employees at commercial banks in Egypt employing KM through the allocation of financial resources and human resources, and instilling a culture of organizational knowledge in order to create effective organizations.
6. Developing the skills and capabilities of officials at commercial banks in Egypt in the field of KM, through specialized training programs that focus on KM as one of the methods that can be used to improve OS, on the one hand, and to achieve competitive advantage, on the other hand.

7. Increasing the interest of officials at commercial banks in Egypt to possess self-knowledge of their employees, through paying attention to selection of new employees who possess knowledge of medical excellence, in addition to providing employees with current medical knowledge in their respective fields, as this reflects the positive impact on the performance of commercial banks in Egypt.
8. Increasing the interest of officials at commercial banks in Egypt, both types of knowledge, implicit and explicit, through the activation of knowledge generation processes, configuration of ideas, experience and skills available to the employees and saving knowledge bases in order to facilitate reference.

7. Prospective Proposed Research

The present study is one of the pioneer works on the subject in Egypt organizational context. It provides evidence, suggests the importance and contributes to the existing body of universal knowledge in areas of KM.

The findings of the research help KM researchers, as well as practitioners, develop a better understanding of the role of OS and successful implementation of KM. The current study may provide necessary guidelines to understand the issues of KM and OS. Also, the findings provide an initial understanding of the way towards further research in this area. Future research may focus on other important areas of OS (organizational survival, and organizational growth) and KM process attributes (Knowledge capitalization, sharing, transformation and capturing).

Further prospective studies on KM and its impact on some variables such as job performance, innovation organizational strategic performance, and effectiveness of managers in different organizations can be applied to other communities, such as private universities, school districts, as well as public and private banks.

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